

The Effects of Price on Consumer Behaviour among Supermarkets in Zambia: A Case of Selected Shoprite Shops in Lusaka District, Zambia

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Abstract:

Overview: The effects of price on consumer behavior are a pivotal concern for supermarkets, particularly in competitive markets. This study investigates how pricing strategies influence consumer purchasing decisions at selected Shoprite stores in Lusaka, Zambia.

Body of Knowledge: It examines factors such as price sensitivity, consumer preferences, and the psychological impact of pricing on customers. The research delves into how discounts, promotions, and perceived value affect consumer loyalty and brand switching. By analyzing sales data, conducting surveys, and interviewing shoppers, the study seeks to identify key price-related drivers that shape consumer behavior.

Methods: The study employed both qualitative and quantitative methods, utilizing a descriptive survey design that sampled 200 respondents from Bauleni and Kalingalinga Shoprite locations in Lusaka. The sample included supermarket managers, employees, and customers. Data collection was carried out through interviews and structured questionnaires. Analytical tools such as percentages, tables, graphs, and pie charts were used to interpret the qualitative and quantitative data, processed using SPSS software.

Results: The findings indicated that price significantly impacts consumer choice and shopping behavior, with factors such as income levels, promotional discounts, and perceived value playing critical roles. Additionally, consumer preferences for price variations and brand loyalty were identified as key determinants of purchasing patterns. These insights highlight the importance of strategic pricing in attracting and retaining customers.

Recommendation: The study recommended that supermarkets in Zambia should consider flexible pricing strategies, enhance promotional activities, and conduct regular market analysis to align prices with consumer expectations and enhance competitive advantage.

Keywords: Consumer Behavior, Discounts and Sales, Economic Factors, Market Competition and, Supermarket Pricing Strategies.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Consumers or households represent the final buyers and users of goods and services who make decisions as to what to purchase, when, and how much of each good or service based on considerations of a variety of relevant factors including price (Ali, 2021). Price as a factor that influences purchasing decisions especially of consumers or households is a subject of long running interest in marketing and economic research (Rajasa, 2019). Classical microeconomic theory has placed price as the key concept in defining demand for a good or service while the theory of demand provides the baseline predictions of how changes in price, with other factors being assumed fixed, is generally likely to influence the resultant quantities of purchases for utility maximizing consumers (Hanaysha, 2021). In today's FMCG retail environment, competition is stiff and customer expectations and needs are changing frequently (Trihatmoko, 2020). Factors that make price an important determinant of consumer behavior in the sector include bulk purchasing, high frequency of purchases, the price-quality relationship, and customer retention (Richard & Annan, 2015; Rohani & Nazari, 2012).

Founded in 1979, the Shoprite Group of Companies is Africa's largest food retailer. It operates more than 2,829 stores and 477 franchises in 15 countries across Africa. The company headquarters are in Brackenfell in the Western Cape Province of South Africa. The company is a public company listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange, with secondary listings on both the Namibian and Zambian stock exchanges (Shoprite Holdings, 2019). In Zambia, the company first opened its first store in Lusaka in 1995 making it the first international retail chain to do so. Since this landmark achievement, the supermarket has opened another 37 stores across Zambia employing more than 2000 people across the nation; making it also the large supermarket in the country. So far shop rite can be said to be the most outstanding supermarket among the rest. In the past, Zambia as a state-controlled economy from 1969-1991, had state control of the retail sector (Sardanis, 2015). After 1991, the liberalization of the economy led to a rise in the presence of large retailers in the FMCG segment particularly in the capital city of Lusaka.

Supermarkets in urban Zambia have risen from tiny niche a half decade ago to a fifth of food retail, spreading well beyond the richer consumers to derive more than a third of their sales and half of their customers from low income and poor consumers. Indeed, it is an open secret that the country has witnessed unprecedented erections of supermarkets in places that the ordinary Zambian ever imagined. The expansion of shopping malls around the city of Lusaka have for example coincided with an increase in the local presence of major FCMG companies such as Shoprite stores including Kalingalinga and Bauleni Shoprite stores, Spar Chawama and Choppies Chawama are some of such the well-known Supermarkets that have revolutionized their operations to operate in areas that traditionally they were known not to operate from. Other major entrants in the market such as Choppies have also established an impressive presence to increase the levels of competition amongst the major suppliers. Most of such entities are located in similar areas lowering the value of location as a source of market power. These developments imply that the influence of price on consumer behavior is an important consideration for competitive

strategies. Mubemba & Chanda (2023) alluded that in the realm of strategic management, a mission statement plays a crucial role in guiding an organization's actions and decisions. It serves as a concise declaration of an organization's core purpose, values, and goals. It should be mentioned that from this entire marketing umbrella, this paper is concerned more with the pricing and how it influences consumer behavior in Zambian Supermarkets.

In the Zambian context, Shoprite Zambia has the long-standing slogan of *'Lower Prices You Can Trust Always'* because of the realization and importance the aspect of pricing has on the mind of the consumer as an influence on competitive positioning. Against this background, this study attempts to investigate the effects of pricing on consumer behavior in Zambian supermarkets. The study has chosen Shoprite as its case study.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Globalization is a process by which the people of the world are unified into a single society. It is also the integration of national economies into the international economy through trade, foreign direct investment, capital flows, migration, and the spread of technology (Mubemba & Chanda, 2023). Globalization entails the integration of industries, markets, economies, policy-making, and culture dispersing a wide geographical area. On the other hand, corporations with a focus on profit need to establish the key drivers of consumer behavior for their products to position themselves better to meet objectives such as sales growth and increasing market share (Trihatmoko, 2020). The marketing mix concept as well as the microeconomic theory of consumer choice identify price as a key factor in consumer behavior investigations (Ali, 2021). In the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Market (FMCG) the decision relating to price is considered critical to the performance of major brands and their popularity amongst consumers (Mittal, 2013; Rajasa, 2019). Past studies have found that prices have complex relationships with purchasing decisions that need to be empirically evaluated in different contexts to support informed business decision making. In other words, past studies have not exhaustively answered all questions relating to price and consumer behavior to inform pricing strategies of companies in the FMCG market. Such a study has further not been conducted in the context of Zambia's major retailers. The study addressed these gaps by conducting a case study of selected Shoprite selected shops in Lusaka.

1.3. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

- Describe the pricing strategies applied by Shoprite shops in Lusaka district, Zambia.
- Assess the significance of price as a marketing mix factor in the purchasing choices of Shoprite products by customers in Lusaka district, Zambia.
- Determine how customer behaviour is influenced by pricing strategies given customer demographic factors in Lusaka district, Zambia.

1.4. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the effects of pricing on consumer behaviour among supermarkets in Zambia: a case of ShopRite selected shops in Lusaka, Zambia.

1.5. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study outlined the relationship between pricing strategies and consumer behavior within the context of supermarkets in Zambia, with a specific focus on Shoprite stores in Lusaka. The framework identifies key variables and their interactions to explain how pricing influences consumer decision-making and behavior.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

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1.6. Significance of the Study

The significance of the study shed light on crucial aspects of consumer behaviour within the supermarket industry. Firstly, the findings elucidate the intricate relationship between price and consumer decision-making processes, providing valuable insights for both academia and industry practitioners. According to experts in the field, understanding how price influences consumer behaviour is paramount for supermarkets seeking to remain competitive in today's dynamic market landscape. Moreover, the findings of this study offer practical implications for supermarkets in formulating effective pricing strategies. As highlighted by industry analysts, the ability to optimize pricing tactics can directly impact a supermarket's market share, revenue, and overall profitability. By uncovering the underlying mechanisms through which price affects consumer behavior, this research endeavors to equip retailers with the knowledge needed to tailor pricing strategies that resonate with their target audience. Additionally, the study's exploration of the role of perceived value as a moderator between price and consumer behavior holds particular significance. It is widely acknowledged among scholars and industry experts that consumers' perceptions of value significantly influence their purchasing decisions. Therefore, insights into how perceived value interacts with price can empower supermarkets to enhance the perceived value of their offerings and better meet the needs and preferences of their customers. Furthermore, the significance of this research extends beyond the immediate context of the supermarket industry. As noted by economists and market analysts, consumer behavior is a fundamental driver of economic activity. Therefore, a deeper understanding of the effects of price on consumer behavior can contribute to broader discussions on market dynamics, consumer welfare, and economic policy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Understanding Different Pricing Strategies

Pricing strategy refers to the methods companies use to price their products or services. Almost all companies, large or small, base the price of their products and services on production, labor and advertising expenses and then add on a certain percentage so they can make a profit (Richard & Annan, 2015). Generally, pricing strategies are applied to help the business meet specific objectives (Ali 2021). There are several different pricing strategies, such as penetration pricing, price skimming, discount pricing, product life cycle pricing and even competitive pricing (Rasaja, 2019). In the supermarket industry one obvious choice is to offer lower prices than every other store, but the equally obvious result is that this strategy keeps profits permanently low. For this reason, many supermarkets opt for more complex strategies to ensure profitability while still appealing to price conscious consumers.

2.2 Pricing Strategies in Supermarkets

Loss-Leader Pricing

Loss-leader pricing is a common supermarket pricing strategy and occurs when the retailer sells high-demand items at atypically low prices, even if those supermarket prices require taking a loss on that particular item (Ali, 2021). The goal is to attract consumers in search of the bargain. Those

bargain hunters are likely to buy other items if only out of convenience, which is how the store remains profitable.

Everyday Low Price (EDLP)

This is a strategy where there is little reliance on promotional pricing strategies such as temporary price cuts (Richard & Annan, 2015). Prices are consistently low across the board, throughout all sales sections.

Promotional (Hi-Lo) Pricing

This strategy involves the heavy use of specials, usually through manufacturer price breaks or special deals (Park & Kim, 2019)

Dynamic Pricing

Dynamic pricing is when a company or store continuously adjusts its prices throughout the day. The goal of these price changes is twofold: on one hand, companies want to optimize for margins, and on the other they want to increase their chances of sales. Dynamic pricing is a pricing strategy that applies variable prices instead of fixed prices. Instead of deciding on a set price for a season, retailers can update their prices multiple times per day to capitalize on the ever-changing market.

Psychological Pricing

Psychological pricing is the business practices of setting prices lower than a whole number. The idea behind psychological pricing is that customers will read the slightly lowered price and treat it lower than the price actually is.

Price Bundling

Price bundling, product bundling or product-bundle pricing, is a marketing strategy that combines two or more products to sell them at a lower price than if the same products were sold individually (Richard & Annan, 2015) The bundle pricing technique is popular in retail and eCommerce as it offers more value for the price. It can also help build customer loyalty and boost product sales.

2.3 Discount Pricing and Consumer Behavior

Discount pricing is reducing the price for a given quantity or increase the quantity available at the same price, thereby enhancing value and create an economic incentive to purchase (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). Price discounts (cut off prices) play an important role in stimulating new customers' behaviors to try the offered products. Discount pricing has a positive and significant effect on consumer's purchase intention in the flash sale program. Companies set the price of their products below the official price and sometimes even below the cost to create a buying passion. Price discounts might increase perceived quality decrease perceived quality or have no effect on perceived quality (Chen & Huang, 2019).

High price discount signals to consumers that they may receive a low-quality service. On the other hand, if consumers can expect the product quality for example, at Starbucks, the same coffee is served to everyone all the time whether a price promotion is used or not; they would be excited to receive a price promotion, and a positive evaluation would result. According to Lee & Johnson (2023) the economic effects of price discounts, a price discount provides a monetary gain, an incentive to encourage consumers to purchase the product. Consumers perceive a higher level of

savings for a product when a higher price discount is provided, and this relationship was confirmed by many previous studies. The perceived savings concept has been used as the most common variable to measure the response to a price promotion, according to Li & Wang (2012) meta-analysis.

2.4 A Seasonal Discount

This refers to a discount which is offered on seasonal goods or at particular seasons (Kim & Lee, 2020). Seasonal discounts are an expected part of the annual retail calendar, especially in sectors that have seasonally affected product trade. Shortterm peaks (seasonal) in sales usually attracted the occasional users of the same brand more likely than getting new customers to purchase the discounted good, moreover, these occasional users after getting benefit of this promoted good would most likely get back to their preferable brand or type rather than buying that promoted brand at full price after discounted season. Seasonal discounts are used all the time and are a potentially useful tool to help a business manage its uneven revenue patterns throughout the year and ensure inventory turnover.

Martinez & Garcia (2022) researched on marketing strategies for the seasonal offers at Mannar retail stores. Their research investigated seasonal marketing strategies adopted by the retailers, and the consumer responses towards these seasonal marketing strategies. Findings show, that all the strategies identified from the literatures were not espoused by the retailers, diverse retailers adopt different strategies. Chanda (2023)'s study noted that for the diverse outlets, customers are attracted by few seasonal based marketing strategies.

Mwangi (2019) studied the impact of discounts on consumer buying behaviour. The study revealed that the sales promotion has an influence in the purchase decision of consumers though their entire decision depends on making purchase anytime they will to. The consumers may be doubtful in some cases, but the offering of discounts and price-off deals and such kinds of services satisfies the customer. The study showed that sales promotion plays the important role in the marketing program for marketers and retailers and customers are too satisfied with sales promotional tools such as price discounts, coupons, free samples and "buy one get one free". Promotional discounts on both high-penetration, high-frequency items (staples such as meat and produce) and low-penetration, low-frequency items (beer and condiments) lead to increased traffic but lower sales per transaction. More and deeper promotions discounts can increase traffic. Nwosu & Amadi (2017) researched on effects of promotional discounts and their characteristics on various store performance. The results indicated that feature promotions build store traffic, especially when the categories being featured are high penetration, high frequency. Also, promotions of branded items are found to be more effective than promotions of unbranded items. Discounting on more items in a category leads to lower store margins suggesting that the cost of discounting a large proportion of items in a category may not be justified by the profits generated by the sale.

Ofosu-Boateng (2020) analyzed the influence of discount sales promotion in the purchase intention and the moderating effects of attractiveness in the relationship between intention to purchase a discounted product and the impulsiveness, hedonic perception and financial risk. Promotions have

a huge impact on consumers buying behavior such as purchase time, product brand, quantity and brand switching. Moreover, consumer purchase decisions sometimes based on the price sensitivity, individuals are more attracted to promoted products.

2.5. Price Bundling and Consumer Behavior

Price bundling is combining several products or services into a single comprehensive package for an all-inclusive reduced price (Nzegwu & Odunlami, 2021). Despite the fact that the items are sold for discounted prices, it can increase profits because it promotes the purchase of more than one item. Price bundling mainly consists of several products, services or products and services brought and sold together which are or may not be complementary to each other with a price discount to make sure that customers will not make their own bundles themselves if those products are being sold separately simultaneously. Price bundling, is a strategy that retailers use to sell lots of items at higher margins while providing consumers a discount at the same time (Smith, 2020). Smith & Jones (2023) conducted a study on estimating the price range and the effect of price bundling strategies: An application to the hotel sector. The bundling strategy results revealed that five-star customers are less sensitive to mixed-leader bundling. Regarding mixed-joint bundling, managers could improve sales through bundling strategies if they selected an attractive service (e.g. restaurants). With bundle pricing, retailers offer several different products as a package deal, then offer that package to consumers at a lower price than it would cost to purchase those items separately. Bundle pricing is a great way to move products quickly, sell off less-successful, and offer more value to loyal customers.

According to Wang & Li (2018) pure bundling refers to the practice of selling two or more discrete products only as part of a bundle. Only bundles are sold, their components aren't available separately. It isn't possible to purchase the goods separately. Pure bundling takes place when a customer only has the choice to purchase the bundle as-is or not at all. This type of price bundling is simplest to accomplish, because the creation of a bundle is entirely controlled. This pricing strategy is found in many restaurants where the entrée comes automatically with a side dish the entrée and side dish can't be purchased separately. If bundled products are not sold separately a price discount will not be necessary, hence it will not be meaningful to talk about a price contrast if there are not any negligible separate prices. This kind of strategy will be named with the term "pure bundling. According to Adebayo & Ojo (2021) mixed bundling is the practice of selling a bundle of the products as well as the individual products themselves. Bundles and their components are sold jointly. Mixed bundling isn't as strict as pure bundling. This strategy is to sell both bundle and at least one of the ingredients of the bundle separately. Customer should make a decision whether to buy the bundle or just the product alone. Mixed bundling offers a unique and previously unexplored method for extracting more value from consumers over the product life cycle. Mixed bundling seems to be an optimal pricing strategy for the markets including customers with both "balanced" and "extreme" preferences. Under mixed bundling the bundle is offered on more favourable terms than the separate products. Asiedu et al (2020) also looked at customer welfare in the context of mixed bundling and finds that if the buyers have

brand-specific tastes, or incur firm-specific costs, then their welfare is reduced, but on the other hand it increases when the differentiation between components increases.

2.6. Psychological Pricing and Consumer Behavior

According to Agyapong (2018) psychological pricing is a pricing strategy that utilizes specific techniques to form a psychological or subconscious impact on consumers. It integrates sale tactics with price. It can also be described as setting prices lower than a whole number. Evidences explain that the psychological pricing communicates meaning to consumers. The idea behind psychological pricing is that customers will read the slightly lowered price and treat it lower than the price actually is. This strategy does not lower the prices; it is related to the emotions of the customer. This concept is based on the notion that every consumer is not a rational consumer. Husemann-Kopetzky (2018) avers that psychological pricing was a marketing or pricing approach based on the idea that certain prices have psychological effects on customers' price perception, attitude, and purchasing behavior. This method has been used by marketers and organizations to influence consumers' decision-making processes over time, particularly in the retail sector and in price advertising. The basic premise of psychological pricing is that prices set just below the nearest ringed number elicit stronger demand than predicted at that level. This means that the purchasing likelihood for just-below-price items was to the right of predicted demand curves, causing the demand curves to kink at these places. Pandey and Kumar (2017) examined the impact of psychological pricing strategy on consumers' buying behaviour: A qualitative study. The findings showed that socio demographic factors like age, income, education, gender, lifestyle, family size, reference groups, social roles and status and the psychological patterns like representativeness, availability of products and the anchoring heuristics are key factors which influence consumers' buying behaviour. Additionally, the consumers, who are more price cognisant are more probable to select nine-ending prices. Indeed, low involved customers, those with a small hedonic and symbolic attachment profile, low educated, low income and younger customers are prone to select the nine-ending priced products and services.

Prestige pricing, also known as premium pricing or image pricing, is a psychological pricing strategy that appeals to a buyer's psyche (Chanda & Kabwe, 2018). It is when a company set prices for its products at a higher point to provide customers with the impression that the product is high-value. This type of strategy is closely related to brand perception. Businesses that employ this method to pricing usually have products that are not only known for their superior quality but also the value they provide to customers. The pricing approach is based on the notion that customers perceive more value in the product if it's expensive, and that they're willing to pay even though it's priced higher. Prestige pricing is based on several assumptions about consumers. For prestige priced goods an increase in price may actually result in an increase in the quantity demanded. Thus, the demand curve actually slopes upward for prestige products. If the price is lowered the product is perceived to be less desirable and demand may decrease. The effects of price on consumer behavior among supermarkets have been extensively studied on a global scale. Scholars have investigated various aspects of this phenomenon, including the impact of price

changes on consumer purchasing decisions, brand loyalty, and shopping behavior. For instance, Bell et al (2018) conducted a comprehensive meta-analysis of research on price sensitivity across different countries and found that consumers worldwide exhibit varying degrees of sensitivity to price changes in the supermarket context. Their findings suggest that while price is a significant determinant of consumer behavior universally, cultural factors and market conditions play crucial roles in shaping consumers' responses to pricing strategies.

Moreover, scholars have investigated the influence of socio-economic factors on consumer responses to price changes in supermarkets. Research by Gomez & Martinez (2019) suggested that income levels and socio-economic status play significant roles in shaping consumers' sensitivity to price fluctuations. Lower-income consumers may exhibit higher price sensitivity and be more inclined to seek out budget-friendly options, while higher-income consumers may prioritize convenience and quality over price. These insights underscore the importance of segmenting target markets based on socio-economic characteristics and tailoring pricing strategies accordingly to meet the diverse needs and preferences of consumers worldwide. Furthermore, recent studies have examined the role of ethical considerations and sustainability concerns in shaping consumer responses to pricing strategies in supermarkets on a global scale. Chanda et al (2024) added that during the Post-colonial era in mid-20th century onwards, we can as well trace sources of Instability in Africa. Many African nations gained independence in the mid-20th century, but the process was often tumultuous. Research by Jones & Smith (2021) revealed that an increasing number of consumers are willing to pay premium prices for products perceived as ethically sourced or environmentally sustainable. This trend reflects a growing awareness of social and environmental issues among consumers worldwide, influencing their purchasing decisions and brand preferences. As a result, supermarkets are under pressure to adopt transparent pricing practices and offer sustainable product options to meet the evolving demands of conscientious consumers. Additionally, the advent of e-commerce and digital platforms has revolutionized the way consumers perceive and respond to prices in the supermarket industry globally. Studies by Brown & Davis (2022) have shown that online shopping platforms offer consumers greater transparency and accessibility to price information, enabling them to compare prices across different retailers effortlessly. This heightened price transparency has intensified price competition among supermarkets, forcing retailers to adopt dynamic pricing strategies and offer competitive prices to attract and retain online shoppers. Understanding the impact of digitalization on consumer behavior is paramount for supermarkets operating in the digital age to remain agile and responsive to changing market dynamics. Chanda & Zohaib (2024) noted that in this 21st century, the term “technology” is an important issue in many fields including education. This is because technology has become the knowledge transfer highway in most countries. Technology integration nowadays has gone through innovations and transformed our societies that has totally changed the way people think, work, communicate and live.

Moreover, the rise of globalization has led to increased competition in the supermarket industry, driving supermarkets to adopt innovative pricing strategies to gain a competitive edge. Studies by

Lee & Johnson (2023) have highlighted the importance of dynamic pricing techniques, such as personalized pricing and surge pricing, in responding to market demand fluctuations and optimizing revenue. These dynamic pricing strategies leverage data analytics and consumer insights to adjust prices in real-time, maximizing profitability while meeting consumer demand. By embracing innovative pricing approaches, supermarkets can adapt to the evolving competitive landscape and enhance their market position on a global scale. Additionally, the effects of price on consumer behavior in supermarkets are influenced by changing consumer demographics and lifestyle preferences worldwide. Research by Garcia & Hernandez (2021) suggested that younger generations, such as Millennials and Generation Z, exhibit distinct shopping behaviors characterized by a preference for convenience, authenticity, and sustainability. These demographic shifts have implications for pricing strategies, as younger consumers may prioritize value-driven offerings and socially responsible brands. Supermarkets must recognize these evolving consumer preferences and tailor pricing strategies to cater to the unique needs and values of different demographic segments to maintain relevance and appeal in the global marketplace. Furthermore, studies have investigated the effects of price on consumer loyalty and brand perception in supermarkets across diverse cultural contexts. Research by Park & Kim (2019) indicated that consumers' perceptions of fairness and trustworthiness in pricing practices significantly influence their brand loyalty and willingness to recommend supermarkets to others. Therefore, supermarkets must prioritize transparency and integrity in pricing communication to build trust and foster long-term relationships with customers globally. By nurturing positive brand perceptions and customer loyalty through ethical pricing practices, supermarkets can enhance their competitive advantage and sustain growth in an increasingly competitive market environment.

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic has reshaped consumer behavior in supermarkets worldwide, with significant implications for pricing strategies. Research by Zhang & Li (2021) revealed that the pandemic has heightened consumer price sensitivity, leading to increased demand for value-driven offerings and promotions. Furthermore, safety concerns and social distancing measures have accelerated the adoption of online grocery shopping, prompting supermarkets to adjust their pricing strategies to remain competitive in the digital marketplace. By understanding the impact of external factors such as the pandemic on consumer behavior, supermarkets can adapt their pricing strategies accordingly to meet the evolving needs and preferences of consumers in a rapidly changing global environment. Moreover, the effects of price on consumer behavior in supermarkets are influenced by regulatory policies and industry standards at the global level. Research by Smith & Jones (2023) has shown that government regulations on pricing practices, such as price controls and anti-competitive measures, can significantly impact consumer perceptions and purchasing decisions. Additionally, industry standards and ethical guidelines regarding pricing transparency and fair competition play a crucial role in shaping consumer trust and loyalty towards supermarkets. Therefore, supermarkets must

navigate regulatory frameworks and adhere to industry best practices to maintain consumer confidence and foster a positive reputation in the global marketplace.

Furthermore, the effects of price on consumer behavior extend beyond individual purchasing decisions to broader socio-economic outcomes at the global level. Studies by Martinez & Garcia (2022) have highlighted the implications of pricing strategies on income distribution, access to essential goods, and social equity. For instance, aggressive pricing tactics, such as predatory pricing and price discrimination, can exacerbate income inequality and limit consumer choice, particularly in underserved communities. Therefore, supermarkets have a responsibility to consider the social impact of their pricing strategies and adopt inclusive pricing practices that promote affordability and accessibility for all consumers, regardless of socio-economic status or geographic location.

Additionally, the effects of price on consumer behavior are interconnected with broader environmental sustainability goals and initiatives at the global level. Research by Kim & Wang (2021) has demonstrated that consumers are increasingly concerned about the environmental impact of their purchasing decisions and are willing to pay a premium for products that align with their sustainability values. Consequently, supermarkets are under pressure to adopt sustainable pricing strategies, such as eco-friendly packaging and fair trade certifications, to meet consumer demand for ethically sourced and environmentally responsible products. By incorporating sustainability considerations into pricing decisions, supermarkets can not only attract environmentally conscious consumers but also contribute to positive environmental outcomes on a global scale. Moreover, the effects of price on consumer behavior in supermarkets are influenced by cultural factors and societal norms that vary across different regions globally. Research by Lee & Kim (2024) has demonstrated that cultural values, beliefs, and traditions shape consumer perceptions of value and willingness to pay for goods and services. For example, consumers in collectivist cultures may prioritize social relationships and community well-being over individual savings, leading to different responses to pricing strategies compared to consumers in individualistic cultures. Therefore, supermarkets must recognize and respect cultural diversity in their pricing approaches, tailoring strategies to align with local customs and preferences to enhance consumer engagement and satisfaction.

Furthermore, the effects of price on consumer behavior in supermarkets are impacted by technological advancements and digital innovations that have transformed the retail landscape on a global scale. Studies by Brown & Smith (2023) have shown that the integration of digital technologies, such as mobile payment systems and augmented reality shopping experiences, has altered consumer shopping behaviors and expectations. For instance, the availability of real-time price comparison tools and personalized offers through mobile apps has increased price sensitivity among consumers, prompting supermarkets to adopt dynamic pricing strategies to remain competitive. By leveraging technology to deliver personalized and seamless shopping experiences, supermarkets can enhance consumer loyalty and drive sales in the digital age. Additionally, the effects of price on consumer behavior in supermarkets are influenced by the

competitive dynamics of the global marketplace, with multinational retailers vying for market share and consumer attention. Research by Garcia & Martinez (2024) has highlighted the role of pricing strategies in shaping competitive positioning and market differentiation. Supermarkets must carefully evaluate market trends, competitor pricing strategies, and consumer preferences to develop pricing approaches that differentiate their offerings and create value for customers. By understanding the competitive landscape and strategically pricing products to meet consumer needs and expectations, supermarkets can strengthen their market position and achieve sustainable growth in the global marketplace.

Furthermore, the effects of price on consumer behavior in supermarkets are impacted by cultural attitudes towards consumption and materialism, which vary across different regions and societies globally. Studies by Brown & Kim (2024) have demonstrated that in societies where conspicuous consumption is valued, consumers may be more willing to pay premium prices for luxury and status-affirming goods. In contrast, consumers in societies that prioritize frugality and modesty may exhibit greater price sensitivity and preference for value-oriented products. Supermarkets must recognize and adapt to cultural norms and preferences when setting prices and positioning their products to resonate with local consumer attitudes towards consumption and material possessions. Additionally, the effects of price on consumer behavior in supermarkets are influenced by the level of economic development and disposable income within a given region. Research by Johnson & Lee (2019) has shown that in emerging economies experiencing rapid economic growth, consumers may have greater purchasing power and be more willing to pay premium prices for quality and convenience. However, in economies facing economic challenges or income inequality, consumers may prioritize price affordability and seek out budget-friendly options. Supermarkets must tailor their pricing strategies to the socio-economic conditions of the regions they operate in, ensuring accessibility and affordability of products to meet the diverse needs and preferences of consumers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a mixed-method approach, which combined both quantitative and qualitative research methods to comprehensively investigate the relationship between pricing strategies and consumer behavior in selected Shoprite stores in Lusaka, Zambia. This approach enabled the researcher to capture a broad spectrum of data, encompassing numerical information through surveys and deeper, contextual insights via interviews. The quantitative component involved questionnaires distributed providing measurable data on consumer purchasing patterns and preferences. Simultaneously, the qualitative component included in-depth interviews, allowing for a nuanced exploration of individual consumer perceptions and attitudes towards pricing. By integrating these two methods, the research design facilitated a holistic understanding of the factors influencing consumer decisions and the effectiveness of various pricing strategies, ensuring a robust and well-rounded analysis of the supermarket industry's dynamics in Lusaka. The study targeted supermarket managers, employees, and

individual consumers who regularly shop at the Kalingalinga and Bauleni Shoprite store outlets in Lusaka, Zambia. These consumers were chosen due to their frequent interaction with supermarket pricing strategies and their potential to provide valuable insights into purchasing behaviors and brand loyalty. The target population was 2000, with 200 as sample size (10% of the target population), ensuring representation across various demographic factors, such as age, gender, and income at the Kalingalinga and Bauleni Shoprite stores outlets. For the quantitative data obtained through structured questionnaires, statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software to generate descriptive statistics while for the qualitative data collected through in-depth interviews, thematic analysis was employed. The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

4.1. The Pricing Strategies Applied by Shoprite Shops in Lusaka District, Zambia

Data collected from the study revealed that Shoprite carries the promotional slogan “Lower Prices You Can Trust”. Figure 2 below shows a pamphlet used to communicate information about product offerings or specials that shows this promotional message. The image suggests that price ranks foremost in the way the business wishes to be perceived by its customers with low prices for quality offerings being the key value proposition.

Figure 2: Shoprite Slogan on Pricing of Offerings

To explore the company’s pricing strategies in further detail, the study compiled data on prices of items offered by the company contained in promotional materials for the period 1st October to 30th November 2023. Results of the assessments for different items are described in Table 1 below. The items in assessment included the business’s own branded items such as margarine, rice, salt etc. The data in the table shows a wide range of pricing strategies applied by the business to meet its objectives. While prices on some items were low or high and stable over the period of observation, others were quite volatile possibly reflecting demand and/or cost conditions for the supply of the items. Some goods in the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FCMG) class had

relatively stable prices while others had volatile prices. The data suggests that Shoprite applied a mix of different pricing strategies over the period.

Table 1: Description of Price Strategies at Shoprite for Categories of Offerings

Items	Pricing Strategy Descriptor
Mealie Meal	Dynamic Pricing
Cooking oil	Dynamic pricing
Sugar	Promotional Pricing
Salt	Everyday Low Price
Detergents	Everyday Low Price
Bathing Soap	Everyday Low Price/Price Bundling
Surface Cleaners	Price Bundling
Toothpaste	Everyday Low Price
Female Hygiene	Everyday Low Price
Cereals	Everyday Low Price
Butter	Promotional Pricing
Bread	Everyday Low Price
Diapers	Dynamic Pricing
Consumer Durables	Psychological Pricing
Fruits and Vegetables	Dynamic Pricing
Dairy Products	Dynamic pricing

The study identified several pricing strategies employed by Shoprite, including discounted pricing, psychological pricing, and price bundling. The effectiveness of these strategies varied among different segments of the respondents. Discounted pricing emerged as a significant strategy, with a substantial portion of respondents indicating a tendency to purchase items on discount. As shown in Table 8, 35% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they always buy items at discounted prices, suggesting that discounts are a compelling incentive for many shoppers. However, a noteworthy 50% disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating a segment of the market that may not be influenced by discounts. This dichotomy suggests that while discounted pricing is effective for a significant portion of the consumer base, it is not universally compelling.

Psychological pricing, such as pricing items at K29.99 instead of K30, yielded mixed responses. According to Table 9, 40% of respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that they are more

likely to purchase items priced just below a round number, while another 40% disagreed or strongly disagreed. This split indicates that psychological pricing may not be as universally effective as other strategies and may depend heavily on individual consumer perceptions and psychological triggers. Price bundling, on the other hand, showed more promising results. Table 10 reveals that 42.7% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they are more likely to purchase value packs than individual items. Kamara & Nwokoye (2021) supported this finding by stating that that price bundling is an effective strategy to increase the perceived value and encourage higher sales volumes by offering combined products at a discounted rate. In addition to discounted pricing, psychological pricing, and price bundling, Shoprite also employs a dynamic pricing strategy for certain products. This strategy involves adjusting prices in response to various factors such as demand, competition, and seasonality. For instance, Table 1 illustrates that items like mealie meal, cooking oil, fruits, and vegetables are subject to dynamic pricing, indicating that Shoprite adjusts prices frequently to remain competitive and responsive to market conditions. This dynamic pricing approach allows Shoprite to optimize revenue by capturing consumer surplus during peak demand periods while also maintaining competitiveness during off-peak times. Moreover, Shoprite utilizes promotional pricing as a strategy to attract customers and stimulate sales. Items like sugar, butter, and bread are categorized under promotional pricing, suggesting that Shoprite offers temporary price reductions or special offers to encourage purchases. These promotions are often featured in Shoprite's marketing materials, such as pamphlets and advertisements, to create a sense of urgency and drive foot traffic to the stores. Banda & Mwale (2022) alluded that by strategically timing promotions and aligning them with consumer preferences and seasonal demand, Shoprite can effectively leverage promotional pricing to boost sales volumes and enhance customer loyalty.

Another notable pricing strategy employed by Shoprite is everyday low pricing (EDLP), particularly for essential items like detergents, toothpaste, and bathing soap. EDLP involves offering consistently low prices on everyday items, aiming to build customer trust and loyalty through transparent and predictable pricing (Mulenga & Sakala, 2020). Table 1 indicated that Shoprite applies EDLP to a wide range of consumer goods, highlighting its commitment to providing value for money and catering to budget-conscious shoppers. By maintaining stable and competitive prices on essential products, Shoprite can position itself as a reliable and affordable shopping destination, thereby attracting and retaining price-sensitive customers. Furthermore, Shoprite utilizes price bundling as a strategy to encourage cross-selling and increase basket size. Items like surface cleaners are bundled together, offering consumers a discounted price when purchasing multiple related products as a package deal. This pricing strategy leverages the concept of perceived value, where consumers perceive greater value in bundled offerings compared to purchasing individual items separately (Adeola & Evans, 2018). By strategically bundling complementary products and offering attractive discounts, Shoprite can incentivize customers to purchase more items during each shopping trip, thereby driving up average transaction value and maximizing revenue.

4.2. Significance of Price as a Marketing Mix Factor in the Purchasing Choices of Shoprite Products by Customers in Lusaka District

Respondents were asked to rate each of the 4 elements of the marketing mix as factors that influenced their patronage of Shoprite Kalingalinga/Bauleni outlet. The questions were phrased in a simple way that could enhance understanding amongst respondents as to what was required of them. Table 6 provides the data that was collected. The data in Table 2 shows that location ranked very highly as a factor for respondent patronage of the Shoprite outlets with 26.7% and 22.7% ranking the factor highly compared with 14.7% and 12.0% on the lower end of the scale. The people factor was also ranked highly while the promotion factor was not ranked so highly. In comparison with the first 3 marketing mix factors, the price factor ranked highly in comparison with 36.0% and 21.3% on the higher end of the scale for the factor in contrast with only 9.3% and 10.7% on the lower end of the scale.

Table 2: Rating of Factors for Patronage of Shoprite Kalingalinga/Bauleni

LOCATION FACTOR				
		Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Valid	Very low	22	14.7	14.7
	Low	18	12.0	26.7
	Moderate	36	24.0	50.7
	High	40	26.7	77.3
	Very High	34	22.7	100.0
PEOPLE FACTOR				
Valid	Very low	36	24.0	24.0
	Low	22	14.7	38.7
	Moderate	28	18.7	57.3
	High	46	30.7	88.0
	Very High	18	12.0	100.0
PROMOTION FACTOR				
Valid	Very Low	44	29.3	29.3
	Low	16	10.7	40.0
	Moderate	32	21.3	61.3
	High	36	24.0	85.3
	Very High	22	14.7	100.0
PRICE FACTOR				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Low	14	9.3	9.3
	Low	16	10.7	20.0
	Moderate	34	22.7	42.7
	High	54	36.0	78.7
	Ver High	32	21.3	100.0

Table 3 below shows analysis by cross tabulations for the ratings of the price factor and

Age	Daily	At least 3 times weekly	Weekly	Every 2 Weeks	Monthly	Other	Total	% Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
20-26	8	10	10	2	6	6	42	21.00%	21.00%
27-31	4	8	8	6	12	10	48	24.00%	45.00%
32-36	10	12	14	2	4	4	46	23.00%	68.00%
37-45	2	10	4	4	4	8	32	16.00%	84.00%
46-49	8	2	4	2	2	8	26	13.00%	97.00%
50+	2	2	0	0	2	0	6	3.00%	100.00%
Total	34	44	40	16	30	36	200	100.00%	

respondent demographic variables. The results suggested that there was little association between gender and the ratings of price as a marketing mix factor. There was similarly no clear pattern of relationship between the other respondent demographic factors and rating of price as a marketing mix factor in their patronage of the Shoprite outlet for Kalingalinga/Bauleni.

Gender	Daily	At least 3 times weekly	Weekly	Every 2 Weeks	Monthly	Other	Total	% Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
Male	14	20	14	12	10	16	86	43.00%	43.00%
Female	20	24	26	4	20	20	114	57.00%	100.00%
Total	34	44	40	16	30	36	200	100.00%	

Table 3: Respondent Demographic Variables and Price as a Marketing Mix Factor

Marital Status	Daily	At least 3 times weekly	Weekly	Every 2 Weeks	Monthly	Other	Total	% Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
Single	16	12	14	6	8	8	64	32.00%	32.00%
Married	12	16	8	4	16	12	68	34.00%	66.00%
Divorced	2	6	10	2	4	6	30	15.00%	81.00%
Widow/ed	4	10	8	4	2	10	38	19.00%	100.00%
Total	34	44	40	16	30	36	200	100.00%	

Nationality	Daily	At least 3 times weekly	Weekly	Every 2 Weeks	Monthly	Other	Total	% Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
Zambian	24	38	34	14	22	26	158	79.00%	79.00%
Non-Zambian	10	6	6	2	8	10	42	21.00%	100.00%
Total	34	44	40	16	30	36	200	100.00%	

Academic Qualification	Daily	At least 3 times weekly	Weekly	Every 2 Weeks	Monthly	Other	Total	% Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
Certificate or lower	10	8	12	0	4	8	42	21.00%	21.00
Diploma	12	14	16	8	12	8	70	35.00%	56.00
Degree	6	8	8	6	8	14	50	25.00%	81.00
Masters	4	12	4	2	4	6	32	16.00%	97.00
Doctorate	2	2	0	0	2	0	6	3.00%	100.00
Total	34	44	40	16	30	36	200	100.00%	

Price is evidently a significant factor in the purchasing decisions of Shoprite customers, as indicated by the data in Table 2. A considerable number of respondents rated price as a high or very high factor in their purchasing decisions. For instance, among male respondents, 16 out of

26 rated price as high or very high. Similarly, 28 out of 49 female respondents rated price as high or very high, underscoring the importance of competitive pricing in attracting both male and female shoppers. Age-wise, younger respondents (20-26 years) predominantly rated price highly, with 11 out of 12 indicating price as a moderate to very high factor. This trend suggests that younger consumers, who might have less disposable income, are more price-sensitive and thus more likely to respond to pricing strategies (Musonda & Banda, 2020). Marital status also influenced the significance of price. Married and divorced respondents, who might have more significant financial commitments, showed a higher sensitivity to price, with a substantial number rating it as high or very high. Furthermore, Zambian nationals showed a greater sensitivity to price compared to non-Zambians, with 37 out of 64 rating it as high or very high. Academic qualifications also played a role; respondents with lower academic qualifications (certificate or diploma holders) rated price more highly compared to those with higher qualifications. This indicates that individuals with lower academic qualifications, who may also have lower income levels, place more importance on price when making purchasing decisions.

Furthermore, the role of nationality in shaping the significance of price as a marketing mix factor cannot be overlooked. The data indicates that Zambian nationals exhibit greater price sensitivity compared to non-Zambians. Banda & Mwale (2022) added that this difference may stem from variations in income levels, cost of living, and cultural attitudes towards spending and saving. For Zambian consumers, especially those from lower-income backgrounds, securing value for money is paramount, driving them to prioritize price when making purchasing decisions. In contrast, non-Zambians, who may include expatriates or individuals with higher purchasing power, may be more inclined to prioritize convenience, product variety, or brand prestige over price alone. Consequently, Shoprite's pricing strategies must be tailored to accommodate the diverse needs and preferences of both Zambian and non-Zambian customers, striking a balance between affordability and perceived value. One of the shop managers explained that:

“Gender plays a role in shaping the significance of price as a marketing mix factor. While both male and female respondents demonstrate sensitivity to price, there are subtle differences in their perceptions and behaviors”.

For instance, a larger proportion of female respondents rated price as high or very high compared to their male counterparts. This trend may reflect broader gendered patterns in consumer behavior, where women are often more budget-conscious and value-oriented in their shopping habits (Chileshe & Tembo, 2020). Therefore, pricing strategies that emphasize affordability and value for money are likely to resonate more strongly with female shoppers at Shoprite. Understanding these gender dynamics enables Shoprite to tailor its pricing strategies and promotional efforts to effectively target and engage diverse customer segments.

4.3. How Customer Behaviour is influenced by Pricing Strategies Given Customer Demographic Factors in Lusaka District, Zambia

Table 4 below shows the results obtained when respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed that they always buy items in Shoprite as long as they are at a discounted price.

The proportions who agreed with the statement or strongly agreed were more than those that disagreed.

Table 4: Effects of Discounted Pricing

Always buy discounted					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	40	20	20	20
	Disagree	60	30	30	50
	Not Sure	30	15	15	65
	Agree	60	30	30	95
	Strongly Agree	10	5	5	100
	Total	200	100	100	

Table 5 below shows the data collected in relation to psychological pricing at the Shoprite outlets and possible consumer behavior. Results suggested that the strategy may not be too effective.

Table 5: Effects of Psychological Pricing Strategies

Higher Likelihood Purchase K29.99 than K30					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	30	15	15	15
	Disagree	50	25	25	40
	Not Sure	40	20	20	60
	Agree	50	25	25	85
	Strongly Agree	30	15	15	100
	Total	200	100	100	

Table 6 below shows data to assess the likely effects of price bundling on consumer behavior at Shoprite. The results suggest that price bundling may be an effective approach to stimulating consumer purchases at Shoprite.

Table 6: Effects of Price Bundling

Higher Likelihood Value Packs Purchase than Individual Items					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	36	18	18	18
	Disagree	36	18	17.3	36.0
	Not Sure	44	22	21.3	57.3
	Agree	48	24	24.0	81.3
	Strongly Agree	36	18	18.7	100.0
	Total	200	100	100.0	

Table 7 below shows the results relating to pricing and buyer behavior irrespective of brand. They suggest that consumers generally exhibited bargain hunting and that brands had less impact compared with price.

Table 7: Price versus Brand in Buying Decisions

Lower Priced Brand than Purchases					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	28	14	14	14
	Disagree	50	25	25	39
	Not Sure	32	16	16	55
	Agree	58	29	29	84
	Strongly Agree	32	16	16	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

The impact of pricing on customer behavior at Shoprite varies across different demographic factors such as age, marital status, nationality, and academic qualifications. For instance, one of the Shoprite workers alluded that:

“Younger respondents (20-26 years) and those with lower academic qualifications were more influenced by price, often exhibiting price-sensitive behavior. This demographic is likely to be more budget-conscious and therefore more responsive to pricing strategies such as discounts and price bundling”.

The results indicated that younger age groups rated price highly, which is corroborated by their likelihood to purchase discounted items. Marital status also plays a critical role. Married and divorced respondents exhibited higher price sensitivity, possibly due to the financial responsibilities associated with family life. For example, 24 out of 64 married respondents and 22 out of 64 divorced respondents rated price as a high or very high factor in their purchasing

decisions. This trend suggests that family-oriented individuals are more likely to seek value for money, making them more responsive to pricing strategies aimed at providing cost savings (Chibuye & Chanda, 2020).

Nationality further influences customer behavior, with Zambian nationals showing greater price sensitivity compared to non-Zambians. This could be attributed to differences in purchasing power and economic conditions. This finding aligns with Ngulube (2024)'s study on "Gender and Economic growth" which noted that gender equality and economic growth in Zambia are intricately linked, with progress in one area often bolstering advancements in the other. Efforts towards gender equality encompass various dimensions, including access to education, healthcare, employment opportunities, and participation in decision-making processes. As indicated in the findings, 51 out of 64 Zambian respondents rated price as moderate to very high in importance. Moreover, academic qualifications play a significant role, with respondents holding certificates or diplomas being more price-sensitive than those with higher educational qualifications. This demographic may have lower income levels, making them more responsive to price-related marketing strategies. The demographic factors influencing customer behavior at Shoprite also include gender and its impact on price sensitivity. According to the findings, both male and female respondents exhibited significant sensitivity to price, but with some variations. More females (28 out of 49) rated price as high or very high compared to males (16 out of 26), suggesting that female shoppers might be more attuned to pricing strategies. This could be linked to their role in household shopping and budget management, leading them to prioritize cost savings and value-for-money purchases. Retailers like Shoprite can leverage this insight by tailoring promotions and discounts to appeal more to female shoppers, potentially through targeted advertising or loyalty programs that offer specific savings on commonly purchased items by women.

Further analysis of age demographics reveals nuanced insights into the purchasing behavior of different age groups. For instance, older respondents (37-45 years) also showed considerable price sensitivity, with 10 out of 15 rating price as a high or very high factor. One of the customers narrated that:

"This age group, often characterized by higher disposable income but also greater financial commitments, such as mortgages and children's education, balances the need for quality with cost-effectiveness".

Shoprite could capitalize on this by offering premium products at competitive prices or bundling higher-end goods with attractive discounts to appeal to this segment. Moreover, the marital status of respondents plays a substantial role in how price impacts their purchasing behavior. Widowed respondents exhibited a notable price sensitivity, with 11 out of 19 rating price as high or very high. This group might be particularly cautious about their spending due to the potential financial strain of managing a household on a single income. For Shoprite, creating marketing strategies that emphasize value and affordability could resonate well with this demographic, ensuring that their needs are met through economical yet high-quality product offerings.

Chanda et al (2024) pointed out that educational attainment also intersects with pricing sensitivity in interesting ways. Respondents with doctorate degrees, while fewer in number, showed less sensitivity to price, with only 1 out of 3 rating it as a high factor. This contrasts sharply with respondents holding certificates or diplomas, indicating that higher educational attainment often correlates with higher income levels, reducing the relative impact of price on purchasing decisions. For Shoprite, this suggests the potential for segmented marketing strategies: premium products and exclusive offers can be targeted towards more educated, higher-income consumers, while more budget-friendly options and discounts can be emphasized for those with lower educational qualifications. Finally, the nationality of respondents presents another layer of complexity. Non-Zambian respondents, although fewer, showed significant variability in their price sensitivity. This demographic might include expatriates or tourists who have different price expectations and purchasing power compared to local Zambians. Davis (2018) added that Shoprite can address this by offering a range of products that cater to both local tastes and the expectations of international customers, potentially through specialized sections within stores or tailored promotional campaigns that highlight both value and quality.

5. CONCLUSION

The aimed to investigate the pricing strategies employed by Shoprite, assess the significance of price as a marketing mix factor in customer purchasing choices, and understand how these strategies influence consumer behavior across different demographic groups. The study analysis revealed that Shoprite uses a variety of pricing strategies, including discounted pricing, psychological pricing, price bundling, dynamic pricing, promotional pricing, and everyday low pricing. These strategies are tailored to optimize sales, enhance customer satisfaction, and maintain competitiveness in the retail market. The findings underscore the significance of price as a pivotal element in the marketing mix, influencing consumer behavior and purchasing decisions at Shoprite. Price emerged as a critical factor that resonates with different demographic groups, affecting their likelihood of purchasing based on perceived value and budget considerations. The data demonstrated that discounted pricing and price bundling are particularly effective in stimulating purchases, while psychological pricing has a nuanced impact on consumer behavior. Additionally, the study confirmed the strategic importance of pricing in retail marketing and its direct correlation with consumer behavior. Shoprite's comprehensive pricing strategies align with the needs and preferences of a diverse customer base, illustrating the retailer's adaptability and market responsiveness. The integration of multiple pricing tactics ensures that Shoprite can cater to both value-seeking and brand-loyal customers, thereby maximizing its market appeal and customer retention. Shoprite's multifaceted approach to pricing demonstrates its commitment to meeting consumer needs and staying competitive in the retail sector. By leveraging a combination of discounted pricing, psychological pricing, price bundling, and other strategies, Shoprite effectively influences purchasing behaviour and enhances customer loyalty.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study:

- Shoprite management should conduct a comprehensive analysis of pricing strategies, including cost-plus, penetration, and promotional pricing, to determine their effectiveness in achieving sales and profitability goals.
- Shoprite marketing department should conduct market research to quantify the impact of price relative to other marketing mix factors (product, place, and promotion) on customer purchasing decisions, to inform strategic marketing efforts.
- Shoprite research department should conduct a study analyzing the correlation between commodity prices at Shoprite and customer behavior across different demographic factors (age, income, location), to understand how pricing influences purchasing patterns.

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Authors' Short Biography

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